

is a key European actor established in 2015 to advance Europe's transition into a sustainable economy. EIT RawMaterials overarching mandate is to support securing the supply of critical raw materials to the European industry by driving innovation along the raw materials value chain. EIT RawMaterials builds on the world's largest network of partners in raw materials and advanced materials.

Three strategic objectives:

- **Closing Materials Loops:** a radical shift from linear to circular thinking,
- **Designing Materials Solutions:** for materials innovation, products and processes,
- **Securing Raw Materials Supply:** collaborating across the whole industrial value chain.

Lighthouses (= large-scale and long-term innovation initiatives):

- **Responsible Sourcing:** key innovation trends:
 - **Batteries:** securing sustainable access to battery raw materials, including lithium, cobalt, nickel, manganese and graphite, through the introduction of smart solutions that reduce the environmental impact and costs for exploration, mining and mineral processing operations.
 - **Magnets and Motors:** securing sustainable access and domestic sourcing of Rare Earth Elements (REE) with advanced exploration, responsible sourcing and mineral processing, addressing environmental challenges and improving the acceptance of mines and operations with SLO.
 - **Hydrogen Technologies:** responsibly sourced, secure, and sustainable supply of Critical Raw Materials such as Platinum Group Metals (PGM), cobalt, strontium, scandium, graphite, titanium, and REE and further strategic resources such as copper, nickel, and aluminium. Specifically, PGMs are essential for fuel cells.

- **Lightweight Materials:** addressing the need to ramp up domestic processing capacities, diversify a sourcing portfolio and increase efficiency to establish cost-effective sourcing alternatives needed for magnesium.
 - **Photovoltaics (PV):** securing access to critical raw materials for the PV industry (boron, bismuth, gallium, germanium, indium, and silicon) with more efficient extraction from primary ores and waste materials, including tailings. Other materials used to manufacture PVs include silver, arsenic, and selenium, which may come with a supply risk.
 - **Electronics (ICT):** targeted exploration and resource efficiency, due diligence and traceability are pivotal aspects in securing access to all critical and strategic elements that are relevant for the above value chains, including tin, tantalum, tungsten, and gold – the so-called 3TGs, following international responsible sourcing standards set by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- **Sustainable Materials:** key innovation trends:
 - **Batteries:** development of batteries with a higher energy density, power, and longer lifetime.
 - **Magnets and Motors:** innovative and advanced processing and manufacturing to enable, amongst other goals, the most energy-efficient wind turbines.
 - **Photovoltaics (solar panels):** projects that increase performance and substitute or reduce costly, critical, and/or toxic materials.
 - **Electronics:** resource-efficient design, miniaturisation, printed electronics, substituting materials with organic compounds, and more.
- **Circular Societies:** key innovation trends:
 - **Batteries:** improving battery recycling capacities to treat increasing volumes of waste batteries on the market and secure Europe's position as a leader in the circular economy.
 - **Magnets and Motors:** industrial symbiosis in the magnet and motor value chain.
 - **Photovoltaics (solar panels):** advanced recycling technologies for recovering crucial materials and metals, upscaling recycling solutions, innovations for lifetime extension of solar panels, and more.

- **Electronics:** efficient collecting and processing of waste electric and electronic equipment (WEEE) to provide a robust, sustainable supply of secondary raw materials.

Calls and programmes:

- **Innovation:** Call for Innovation & Education Projects (KAVA- KIC- Knowledge and Innovation Communities Added Value Activity call), Open Innovation: <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/innovation/>
- **Entrepreneurship:** Lab2Market, EIT Jumpstarter, Regional Innovation Competition, RawMaterials Accelerator, Booster Call, Open Innovation Challenge: <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/entrepreneurship/>
- **Academy:** Master's Education, PhD Education, Lifelong Learning, Wider Society Learning: <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/academy/>

More information about EIT RawMaterials: <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/>

Contact:

dr. Romana Jordan, Assistant Director for EU Affairs, Romana.Jordan@ijs.si
Nataša Lambergar, International project office, natasa.lambergar@ijs.si

Source: <https://eitrawmaterials.eu/>, February 2024

